

Neutralizing Antibodies for Infectious Diseases

Creative Diagnostics offers a comprehensive selection of neutralizing antibodies to combat infectious disease pathogens. These antibodies can be utilized in various applications including ELISA assay kits, neutralization experiments, WB, IHC, and other related processes. We can also provide services such as host switching and antibody modification tailored to your specific needs. Our proprietary cloning platform allows us to produce high-quality recombinant versions of these antibodies, which are valuable reagents for vaccine development and diagnostic research.

Features and Benefits

- Applications: Neut, WB, ELISA, IHC, IF, Func, etc.
- High sensitivity and specificity: precise binding of surface antigens.
- Batch-to-batch stability: minimal batch-to-batch variation.
- Customizable: recombinant antibodies can be customized.

Ordering Information

Cat_N	Product Name	Antibody Isotype	Applications
Adenovirus (AAV)			
CABT-YN1101	Anti-AAV2 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG3	ELISA, IF, IHC, IP, Neut
CABT-YN1102	Anti-AAV1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	ELISA, IF, IHC, IP, Neut
CABT-YN1104	Anti-AAV4 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	ELISA, IF, IHC, IP, Neut
CABT-YN1105	Anti-AAV8 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	ELISA, IF, IHC, IP, Neut
CABT-YN1106	Anti-AAV5 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	ELISA, IF, IHC, IP, Neut
CABT-NS1231	Anti-ADV5 Hexon Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	FuncS, Neut, SPR, Crystallization
CABT-NS1232	Anti-ADV5 Hexon Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	FuncS, Neut, SPR, Crystallization
CABT-YN1107	Anti-Adenovirus Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	ICC, IF, IHC, ELISA, BL, Neut, LFA

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Alphaviruses			
CABT-YN1254	Anti-Alphaviruses E2 Glycoprotein B Domain Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA, BL
CABT-YN1330	Anti-Alphaviruses E2 Glycoprotein B Domain Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA, BL
Astrovirus			
CABT-NS1001	Anti-Astrovirus Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Human, Fab fragment	Neut, ELISA, WB, SPR
CABT-NS1002	Anti-Astrovirus Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Mouse, Fab fragment	Neut, ELISA, WB, SPR
Baculovirus			
CABT-YN1108	Anti-Baculovirus gp64 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	BL, Neut
BK Polyomavirus (BKV)			
CABT-NS1020	Anti-BKV VP1 Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1021	Anti-BKV Polyomavirus VP1 Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1022	Anti-BKV Polyomavirus VP1 Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Neut, ELISA
Bovine Coronavirus (BCoV)			
CABT-NS1015	Anti-BCoV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	EIA, Neut, ELISA, IF
CABT-NS1016	Anti-BCoV Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG1	EIA, Neut, ELISA, IF
CABT-NS1017	Anti-BCoV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Neut, WB, ELISA
Bovine Viral Diarrhea Virus (BVDV)			
CABT-YN1037	Anti-BVDV1 E2 gp53 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	Neut, IF
CABT-YN1038	Anti-BVDV1/2 gp53 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	Neut, IF
Bundibugyo Virus			
CABT-NS1018	Anti-Bundibugyo Virus Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1019	Anti-Bundibugyo Virus Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
Bunyavirus			
CABT-YN1263	Anti-SFTSV Glycoprotein N Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, WB
CABT-YN1339	Anti-SFTSV Glycoprotein N Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, WB

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Canine Parvovirus (CPV)			
CABT-NS1052	Anti-CPV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1053	Anti-CPV Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1054	Anti-CPV Capsid Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	IP, Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1055	Anti-CPV Capsid Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	IP, Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1056	Anti-CPV Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1057	Anti-CPV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut
Chikungunya Virus (CHIKV)			
CABT-NS1041	Anti-CHIKV E1 and E2 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1042	Anti-CHIKV E1 and E2 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut
CABT-YN1111	Anti-CHIKV Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ChIP, ICC, IF, BL, Neut
CABT-YN1112	Anti-CHIKV E2 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	ELISA, IF, Neut, WB
CABT-YN1201	Anti-CHIKV E2 Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, Neut
CABT-YN1202	Anti-CHIKV E2 Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, Neut
Crimean–Congo Hemorrhagic Fever Virus (CCHFV)			
CABT-NS1039	Anti-CCHFV Gc Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1040	Anti-CCHFV Gc Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut
Cytomegalovirus (CMV)			
CABT-NS1043	Anti-CMV Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1044	Anti-CMV Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1045	Anti-CMV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1046	Anti-CMV Glycoprotein B Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	WB, Neut, ELISA, SPR
CABT-NS1047	Anti-CMV Glycoprotein B Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	WB, Neut, ELISA, SPR
CABT-YN1117	Anti-CMV 66 kDa Cytoplasmic/Nuclear Antigen Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	WB, ICC, IF, ELISA, Neut, Inhib
CABT-YN1118	Anti-CMV gH Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	ICC, IF, IHC-Fr, IP, ELISA, Neut, Inhib
CABT-YN1119	Anti-CMV gB Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	ELISA, Neut, WB
CABT-YN1121	Anti-CMV UL146 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	WB, BL, Neut

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CABT-YN1122	Anti-CMV 66kD Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	ELISA, IF, Neut
CABT-NS1112	Anti-HCMV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	IP, Neut, WB, ELISA, FC
CABT-NS1113	Anti-HCMV gB Monoclonal Antibody	Rat, IgG2a	IP, Neut, ELISA, IF
CABT-NS1114	Anti-HCMV gB Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	IP, Neut, ELISA, IF
CABT-NS1117	Anti-HCMV Pentamer (gH/gL/UL128/UL130/UL131A) Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Human, Fab Fragment	Neut
CABT-NS1118	Anti-HCMV Pentamer (gH/gL/UL128/UL130/UL131A) Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Mouse, Fab Fragment	Neut

Dengue Virus (DENV)

CABT-NS1058	Anti-DENV Env DIII Monoclonal Antibody	Ferret, IgG1	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1059	Anti-DENV Env DI/DII Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1060	Anti-DENV 2 Env Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1061	Anti-DENV 2 Env Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1062	Anti-DENV 4 Env Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	I-ELISA, Neut, Inhib
CABT-NS1063	Anti-DENV 4 Env Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	I-ELISA, Neut, Inhib
CABT-NS1064	Anti-DENV Env Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, Neut
CABT-NS1065	Anti-DENV Env Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a/k	ELISA, Neut
CABT-NS1066	Anti-DENV1 NS1 Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Human, Fab	Inhib, FuncS
CABT-NS1067	Anti-DENV1 NS1 Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Mouse, Fab	Inhib, FuncS
CABT-NS1068	Anti-DENV2 Env Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, BL
CABT-NS1069	Anti-DENV2 Env Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, BL

Eastern Equine Encephalitis Virus (EEEV)

CABT-NS1085	Anti-EEEV E2 Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Human, Fab fragment	Neut
CABT-NS1086	Anti-EEEV E2 Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Mouse, Fab fragment	Neut

Ebolavirus (EBOV)

CABT-NS1072	Anti-EBOV Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	FuncS, Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1073	Anti-EBOV Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	FuncS, Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1074	Anti-EBOV Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	FuncS, Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1075	Anti-EBOV Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA

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CABT-NS1076	Anti-EBOV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1079	Anti-EBOV GP Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, Inhib
CABT-NS1080	Anti-EBOV GP Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, Inhib
CABT-YN1235	Anti-Pan-Ebolavirus Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1312	Anti-Pan-Ebolavirus Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
Enterovirus			
CABT-NS1048	Anti-Coxsackievirus A6 VP1 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, Inhib, ELISA
CABT-NS1049	Anti-Coxsackievirus A6 VP1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Neut, Inhib, ELISA
CABT-NS1050	Anti-Coxsackievirus A16 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, Neut
CABT-NS1051	Anti-Coxsackievirus A16 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	ELISA, Neut
CABT-YN1113	Anti-Coxsackievirus-A9 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	ELISA, IF, Neut
CABT-YN1114	Anti-Coxsackievirus-B3 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	ELISA, IF, Neut
CABT-YN1115	Anti-Coxsackievirus-B4 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	IF, Neut
CABT-YN1116	Anti-Coxsackievirus-B6 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	IF, Neut
CABT-NS1087	Anti-EV71 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1088	Anti-EV71 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1089	Anti-EV71 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1090	Anti-EV71 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1091	Anti-EV71 VP1 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	EM, ELISA, Neut
CABT-NS1092	Anti-EV71 VP1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	EM, ELISA, Neut
CABT-YN1041	Anti-EV71 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	FuncS, IF
CABT-YN1042	Anti-EV71 VP4 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Neut
Epstein-Barr Virus (EBV)			
CABT-NS1083	Anti-EBV gH/gL Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1084	Anti-EBV gH/gL Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut
Feline Leukemia Virus (FeLV)			
CABT-YN1162	Anti-FeLV gp70 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	ELISA, Neut, WB

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Flavivirus			
CABT-NS1093	Anti-Flavivirus Monoclonal Antibody	Ferret, IgA	IHC-P, Neut, WB, ELISA, FC, IF
CABT-NS1094	Anti-Flavivirus NS1 Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Human, Fab Fragment	Neut
CABT-NS1095	Anti-Flavivirus NS1 Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Mouse, Fab Fragment	Neut
CABT-YN1129	Anti-Flavivirus Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	ELISA, FC, IF, IHC, Neut, WB
CABT-YN1130	Anti-Flavivirus Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	ELISA, FC, IF, IHC, Neut, WB
CABT-YN1131	Anti-Flavivirus Env Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	ELISA, FC, IF, IHC, Neut, WB
Foot-and-mouth Disease Virus (FMDV)			
CABT-NS1096	Anti-FMDV VP1 Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1097	Anti-FMDV VP1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1098	Human Anti-FMDV Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Crystallization, Neut
CABT-NS1099	Mouse Anti-FMDV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Crystallization, Neut
Hantavirus			
CABT-NS1100	Anti-Hantavirus Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, Neut
CABT-NS1101	Anti-Hantavirus Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	ELISA, Neut
CABT-YN1249	Anti-Hantavirus (PUUV) C Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1325	Anti-Hantavirus (PUUV) C Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
Hendra virus (HeV) and Nipah Virus (NiV)			
CABT-NS1236	Anti-HeV and NiV Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Neut
CABT-NS1237	Anti-HeV and NiV Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1238	Anti-HeV and NiV Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
Hepatitis A (HAV)			
CABT-NS1102	Anti-HAV VP3 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, Crystallization, EM
CABT-NS1103	Anti-HAV VP3 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, Crystallization, EM
Hepatitis B (HBV)			
CABT-NS1104	Anti-HBcAg Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut

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CABT-NS1105	Anti-HBcAg Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1108	Anti-HBsAg Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	WB, ELISA, Neut
CABT-NS1109	Anti-HBsAg Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	WB, ELISA, Neut
CABT-NS1110	Anti-HBV Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1111	Anti-HBV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut
Hepatitis C (HCV)			
CABT-NS1121	Anti-HCV E1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	FuncS, Neut, ELISA, FC, IF
CABT-NS1122	Anti-HCV E1 Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	FuncS, Neut, ELISA, FC, IF
CABT-NS1123	Anti-HCV E1 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	FuncS, Neut, ELISA, FC, IF
CABT-NS1124	Anti-HCV E2 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	FuncS, IP, Neut, BL, ELISA
CABT-NS1125	Anti-HCV E2 Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	FuncS, IP, Neut, BL, ELISA
CABT-NS1126	Anti-HCV E2 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	FuncS, IP, Neut, BL, ELISA
CABT-NS1127	Anti-HCV E1E2 Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	IP, Neut, ELISA, FC
CABT-NS1128	Anti-HCV E1E2 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	IP, Neut, ELISA, FC
CABT-NS1129	Anti-HCV E1E2 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	IP, Neut, ELISA, FC
CABT-YN1132	Anti-HCV1 NS5B Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	ICC, IF, IP, Neut, Inhib
Herpes Simplex Virus (HSV)			
CABT-NS1293	Anti-HSV-1 VP5 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	FuncS, IP, WB, ELISA, IF
CABT-NS1294	Anti-HSV-1 VP5 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	FuncS, IP, WB, ELISA, IF
CABT-NS1295	Anti-HSV-1 VP5 Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	FuncS, IP, WB, ELISA, IF
CABT-NS1296	Anti-HSV gD Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Neut, FC, IF
CABT-NS1297	Anti-HSV gD Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut, FC, IF
CABT-NS1298	Anti-HSV gD Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, FC, IF
CABT-NS1299	Anti-HSV-2 gD Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, Inhib
CABT-NS1300	Anti-HSV-2 gD Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1k	Neut, Inhib
Bovine Herpesvirus Type 1 (BoHV-1)			
CABT-YN1110	Anti-BoHV-1 gB Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	ELISA, IF, IP, Neut

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Human Coronavirus (HCoV)			
CABT-NS1119	Anti-HCoV OC43 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1120	Anti-HCoV OC43 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut
CABT-YN1086	Anti-HCoV-NL63 RBD Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	WB, Neut, ICC, IF, BL
CABT-NS1350	Anti-MERS-CoV Spike Protein S1 Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1351	Anti-MERS-CoV Spike Protein S1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	Neut
CABT-NS1352	Anti-MERS-CoV Spike Protein S1 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgM	Neut
CABT-YN1088	Anti-MERS-CoV RBD Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	BL, Neut, ICC, IF
CABT-YN1163	Anti-MERS Spike Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	BL, Neut
CABT-YN1225	Anti-MERS-CoV RBD and S1 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1226	Anti-MERS-CoV RBD Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1227	Anti-MERS-CoV Spike Antigen S2 Subunit Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1302	Anti-MERS-CoV RBD and S1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1304	Anti-MERS-CoV Spike Antigen S2 Subunit Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1373	Anti-SARS-CoV S Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgM	Neut, WB, ELISA, IF
CABT-NS1374	Anti-SARS-CoV S Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgM	Neut, WB, ELISA, IF
CABT-NS1375	Anti-SARS-CoV S Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut, WB, ELISA, IF
CABT-YN1089	Anti-SARS-CoV RBD Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	BL, Neut, ICC, IF
CABT-NS1376	Anti-SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	FuncS, BL, ELISA
CABT-NS1377	Anti-SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	FuncS, BL, ELISA
CABT-NS1378	Anti-SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	FuncS, BL, ELISA
CABT-NS1379	Anti-SARS-CoV-2 Spike RBD Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Inhib, Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1380	Anti-SARS-CoV-2 Spike RBD Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	Inhib, Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1381	Anti-SARS-CoV-2 Spike RBD Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Inhib, Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1094	Anti-SARS-CoV-2 RBD Monoclonal Antibody	Llama,	BL, Neut
CABT-YN1096	Anti-SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein (RBD Epitope A) Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	BL, FC, ELISA
CABT-YN1097	Anti-SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein (RBD Epitope B) Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	BL, FC, ELISA

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Human Herpesvirus			
CABT-YN1135	Anti-Human Herpesvirus 8 MIP1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	WB, BL, Neut
CABT-YN1136	Anti-Human Herpesvirus 8 MIP1 PAb	Goat, IgG	WB, BL, Neut
Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV)			
CABT-NS1240	Anti-HIV-1 gp120 Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	FuncS, Neut, WB, ELISA, FC
CABT-NS1241	Anti-HIV-1 gp120 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	FuncS, Neut, WB, ELISA, FC
CABT-NS1242	Anti-HIV-1 gp120 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	FuncS, Neut, WB, ELISA, FC
CABT-NS1243	Anti-HIV Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1244	Anti-HIV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1245	Anti-HIV gp120 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, FC, ELISA
CABT-NS1246	Anti-HIV gp120 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Neut, FC, ELISA
CABT-NS1247	Anti-HIV gp160 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1248	Anti-HIV gp160 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, Neut	
CABT-NS1249	Anti-HIV gp41 Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Human, Fab fragment	Neut
CABT-NS1250	Anti-HIV gp41 Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Mouse, Fab fragment	Neut
CABT-NS1251	Anti-HIV-1 Rev Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1252	Anti-HIV-1 Rev Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse,	Neut
CABT-NS1253	Anti-HIV-1 Capsid Protein p24 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1254	Anti-HIV-1 Capsid Protein p24 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1255	Anti-HIV-1 Envelope Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Human, Fab fragment	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1256	Anti-HIV-1 Envelope Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Mouse, Fab fragment	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1257	Anti-HIV-1 gp120 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, WB, Neut
CABT-NS1258	Anti-HIV-1 gp120 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	ELISA, WB, Neut
CABT-YN1134	Anti-HIV Protease PAb	Rabbit, IgG	WB, IP, ELISA, Neut, Inhib
CABT-YN1137	Anti-HIV-1 CD4bd (gp120) Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, FC, Neut

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CABT-YN1138	Anti-HIV-1 gp41 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	WB, ELISA, FC, BL, Neut, Inhib
CABT-YN1139	Anti-HIV-1 gp41 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	FC, BL, Neut, Inhib
CABT-YN1141	Anti-HIV-1 gp120 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	ELISA, IC, IHC, IP, Neut, WB
CABT-YN1142	Anti-HIV-1 gp120 Strain IIIB PAb	Rabbit, IgG	ELISA, IC, IHC, IP, Neut, WB
CABT-YN1143	Anti-HIV-1 gp120 Strain IIIB Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	ELISA, IC, IHC, IP, Neut, WB
CABT-YN1144	Anti-HIV-1 p66 Strain IIIB Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	ELISA, IC, IHC, IP, Neut, WB
CABT-YN1145	Anti-HIV-1 Tat Strain IIIB Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	ELISA, IC, IP, Neut, WB
CABT-YN1146	Anti-HIV-1 V2 (gp120) Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, Neut
CABT-YN1147	Anti-HIV-1 V3 (gp120) Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, Neut
CABT-YN1148	Anti-HIV-1 Vif Strain IIIB Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	ELISA, IC, IP, Neut, WB
Human Papillomavirus (HPV)			
CABT-NS1271	Anti-HPV16 L1 Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Human, Fab fragment	Neut
CABT-NS1272	Anti-HPV16 L1 Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Mouse, Fab fragment	Neut
CABT-NS1273	Anti-HPV16 VLPs Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Human, Fab fragment	Neut
CABT-NS1274	Anti-HPV16 VLPs Monoclonal Antibody Fab Fragment	Mouse, Fab fragment	Neut
CABT-NS1275	Anti-HPV58 L1 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1276	Anti-HPV58 L1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1277	Anti-HPV58 VLPs Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1278	Anti-HPV58 VLPs Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1279	Anti-HPV59 L1 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1280	Anti-HPV59 L1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1281	Anti-HPV6 L1 Monoclonal Antibody	Human	Neut
CABT-NS1282	Anti-HPV6 L1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse	Neut
CABT-NS1283	Anti-HPV16 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1284	Anti-HPV16 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut
Human Parainfluenza Virus (HPIV)			
CABT-NS1267	Anti-HPIV3 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA

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CABT-NS1268	Anti-HPIV3 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1169	Anti-HPIV Type 3 69kDa Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	IF, Neut, HAI
CABT-YN1168	Anti-HPIV Type 3 69kDa Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	IF, Neut, HAI
Human Rhinovirus			
CABT-NS1285	Anti-Human Rhinovirus 14 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	Neut
CABT-NS1286	Anti-Human Rhinovirus 14 Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1287	Anti-Human Rhinovirus 2 VP2 Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut, WB, IP, IHC
CABT-NS1288	Anti-Human Rhinovirus 2 VP2 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	Neut, WB, IP, IHC
CABT-NS1289	Anti-HRV VP6 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, Inhib
CABT-NS1290	Anti-HRV VP6 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, Inhib
Feline Immunodeficiency Virus (FIV)			
CABT-YN1128	Anti-Feline Immunodeficiency Virus Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	WB, FC, Neut, Inhib
Influenza Virus (IAV/IBV)			
CABT-NS1301	Anti-IAV H1N1 and H2N2 HA Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	IP, Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1302	Anti-IAV H1N1 and H2N2 HA Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	IP, Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1303	Anti-IAV H5N1 HA Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1304	Anti-IAV HA Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1305	Anti-IAV HA1 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	FuncS, ELISA, FC
CABT-NS1306	Anti-IAV HA1 Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	FuncS, ELISA, FC
CABT-NS1307	Anti-IAV HA Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	HAI, Neut, ELISA, IF
CABT-NS1308	Anti-IAV HA Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	HAI, Neut, ELISA, IF
CABT-NS1309	Anti-IAV HA Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, FuncS
CABT-NS1310	Anti-Group 2 Influenza HA Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, Neut
CABT-NS1311	Anti-Group 2 Influenza HA Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	ELISA, Neut
CABT-NS1312	Anti-IAV H1N1 (2009) Neuraminidase Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, Inhib, Neut

Neutralizing Antibodies for Infectious Diseases

Cat_N	Product Name	Antibody Isotype	Applications
CABT-NS1313	Anti-IAV H1N1 (2009) Neuraminidase Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	ELISA, Inhib, Neut
CABT-NS1314	Anti-IAV H1N1 (A/Brevig Mission/1/1918) Neuraminidase Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Inhib
CABT-NS1315	Anti-IAV H1N1 (A/Brevig Mission/1/1918) Neuraminidase Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Inhib
CABT-NS1316	Anti-IAV Hemagglutinin H1 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ABA, Neut, Inhib
CABT-NS1317	Anti-IAV Hemagglutinin H1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	ABA, Neut, Inhib
CABT-NS1318	Anti-IAV H2N2 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, Neut
CABT-NS1319	Anti-IAV H2N2 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	ELISA, Neut
CABT-NS1320	Anti-IAV H3N2 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Inhib, ELISA, Neut
CABT-NS1321	Anti-IAV H3N2 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Inhib, ELISA, Neut
CABT-NS1322	Anti-IAV Hemagglutinin H5 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	FuncS, Inhib, Neut
CABT-NS1323	Anti-IAV Hemagglutinin H5 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	FuncS, Inhib, Neut
CABT-NS1324	Anti-IAV H5N1 HA Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, HAI, Neut
CABT-NS1325	Anti-IAV H5N1 HA Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	ELISA, HAI, Neut
CABT-NS1326	Anti-IAV H7 Hemagglutinin (A/Anhui/1/2013) Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	HAI, Neut
CABT-NS1327	Anti-IAV H7 Hemagglutinin (A/Anhui/1/2013) Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	HAI, Neut
CABT-NS1328	Anti-IAV H7N9 (A/Shanghai/02/2013) Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	HAI, Neut
CABT-NS1329	Anti-IAV H7N9 (A/Shanghai/02/2013) Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	HAI, Neut
CABT-NS1330	Anti-IAV Hemagglutinin H3 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1331	Anti-IAV Hemagglutinin H3 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1332	Anti-IAV H7N2 HA (A/New York/107/2003) Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1333	Anti-IAV H7N2 HA (A/New York/107/2003) Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1334	Anti-IAV H3N2 HA Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, HAI
CABT-NS1335	Anti-IAV H3N2 HA Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, HAI
CABT-YN1152	Anti-IAV H5N1 Hemagglutinin Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, HAI

Neutralizing Antibodies for Infectious Diseases

Cat_N	Product Name	Antibody Isotype	Applications
CABT-YN1153	Anti-IAV H5N1 Hemagglutinin Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	WB, ELISA, BL, Neut
CABT-YN1154	Anti-IAV H1N1 Hemagglutinin Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	ELISA, HAI, Neut, IF, ELISA, WB
CABT-YN1155	Anti-IAV H10N8 Hemagglutinin Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	BL, Neut
CABT-YN1156	Anti-IAV H1N1 M2 (A/WSN/1933) Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	WB, FC, ICC, IF, IP, BL, Neut
CABT-YN1157	Anti-IAV H5N1 Hemagglutinin Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1a	HAI, ELISA
CABT-YN1160	Anti-IAV H7N7 Hemagglutinin Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	ELISA, BL, Neut
CABT-YN1161	Anti-IAV H7N9 Hemagglutinin Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	FC, BL, Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1203	Anti-IAV HA Globular Head Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, FC
CABT-YN1204	Anti-IAV HA Globular Head Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, FC, Neut
CABT-YN1214	Anti-IAV Group 1 and Group 2 Neuraminidase Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, Inhib, FuncS, Neut
CABT-YN1291	Anti-IAV Group 1 and Group 2 Neuraminidase Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	ELISA, NI, FuncS, Neut
CABT-NS1336	Anti-IBV Neuraminidase Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA, ABA
CABT-NS1337	Anti-IBV Neuraminidase Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA, ABA
Japanese Encephalitis Virus (JEV)			
CABT-YN1215	Anti-JEV Envelope Proteins Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, FuncS, BL, ELISA, HAI, ADCC, IFA
CABT-YN1292	Anti-JEV Envelope Proteins Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, FuncS, BL, ELISA, IFA
Junin Virus			
CABT-NS1340	Anti-Junin Virus Glycoprotein 1 Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1216	Anti-Junin Virus GP1 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1293	Anti-Junin Virus GP1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
La Crosse Encephalitis Virus (LACV)			
CABT-NS1341	Anti-LACV G1 Envelope Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	IP, Neut, WB, ELISA, FC
CABT-NS1342	Anti-LACV G1 Envelope Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	IP, Neut, WB, ELISA, FC

Neutralizing Antibodies for Infectious Diseases

Cat_N	Product Name	Antibody Isotype	Applications
CABT-NS1343	Anti-LACV G1 Envelope Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	IP, Neut, WB, ELISA, FC
Lassa Virus			
CABT-YN1217	Anti-Lassa Virus GPC Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1294	Anti-Lassa Virus GPC Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1344	Anti-Lassa Mammarenavirus Glycoprotein Complex Monoclonal Antibody	Cynomolgus monkey, IgG1	Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1345	Anti-Lassa Mammarenavirus Glycoprotein Complex Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgM	Neut, WB, ELISA
Machupo Virus			
CABT-YN1220	Anti-Machupo Virus GP1 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1297	Anti-Machupo Virus GP1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
Marburg Virus (MARV)			
CABT-NS1346	Anti-MARV Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, Fab fragment	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1347	Anti-MARV VP35 Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Inhib, ELISA
CABT-NS1348	Anti-MARV VP35 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Inhib, ELISA
CABT-NS1349	Anti-MARV VP35 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Inhib, ELISA
CABT-YN1221	Anti-MARV Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA, BL
CABT-YN1251	Anti-MARV Glycoprotein RBS Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1298	Anti-MARV Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA, BL
CABT-YN1327	Anti-MARV Glycoprotein RBS Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
Mayaro Virus			
CABT-YN1222	Anti-Mayaro Virus E2 B Domain Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA, FC, IF
CABT-YN1299	Anti-Mayaro Virus E2 B Domain Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA, FC, IF
Metapneumovirus			
CABT-NS1261	Anti-hMPV Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, WB, Neut
CABT-NS1262	Anti-hMPV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	ELISA, WB, Neut
CABT-NS1263	Anti-hMPV F Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut

Neutralizing Antibodies for Infectious Diseases

Cat_N	Product Name	Antibody Isotype	Applications
CABT-NS1264	Anti-hMPV F Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut
Molluscum Contagiosum Virus			
CABT-YN1164	Anti-MCV2 Chemokine-Like Protein PAb	Goat, IgG	WB, BL, Neut
Murine Polyomavirus			
CABT-YN1230	Anti-Murine Polyomavirus Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-YN1307	Anti-Murine Polyomavirus Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
Newcastle Disease Virus (NDV)			
CABT-YN1165	Anti-NDV HN Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgM	HAI, ELISA
CABT-YN1166	Anti-NDV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	ELISA, HAI
CABT-YN1167	Anti-NDV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	ELISA, HAI
Nipah Virus (NiV)			
CABT-NS1239	Anti-NiV gF Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	FuncS, Neut
CABT-YN1232	Anti-NiV Glycoprotein Ectodomain Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1233	Anti-NiV F Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, BL
CABT-YN1309	Anti-NiV Glycoprotein Ectodomain Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1310	Anti-NiV F Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, BL
Norovirus (NoV)			
CABT-NS1353	Anti-NoV GII.4 P Domain Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, BL, ELISA
CABT-NS1354	Anti-NoV GII.4 VP1 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1355	Anti-NoV GII.4 VP1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1357	Anti-NoV GII.4 P Domain Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgA	Inhib
CABT-YN1228	Anti-Murine NoV-1 Capsid P Domain Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA, BL
CABT-YN1234	Anti-NoV GII.4 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, Inhib
CABT-YN1305	Anti-Murine NoV-1 Capsid P Domain Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA, BL
CABT-YN1311	Anti-NoV GII.4 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, Inhib

Neutralizing Antibodies for Infectious Diseases

Cat_N	Product Name	Antibody Isotype	Applications
Parvovirus			
CABT-NS1358	Anti-Parvovirus Monoclonal Antibody	Dog, IgG2	IP, Neut, RIA, ELISA, EM
CABT-YN1236	Anti-Parvovirus Caspid A Epitope Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1237	Anti-Parvovirus Caspid B Epitope Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1238	Anti-Parvovirus B19 VLP Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1313	Anti-Parvovirus Caspid A Epitope Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1314	Anti-Parvovirus Caspid B Epitope Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1315	Anti-Parvovirus B19 VLP Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
Poliovirus			
CABT-YN1045	Anti-Poliovirus Type 3 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1278	Anti-Poliovirus Type 1 VP1 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1354	Anti-Poliovirus Type 1 VP1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	Neut, ELISA
Porcine Circovirus (PCV)			
CABT-YN1244	Anti-PCV Type 2 Cap Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1321	Anti-PCV Type 2 Cap Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
Porcine Endogenous Retrovirus (PERV)			
CABT-NS1359	Anti-PERV Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1360	Anti-PERV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	Neut, WB, ELISA
Powassan Virus (POWV)			
CABT-NS1361	Anti-POWV Env Domain III Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut, ELISA, FC
CABT-NS1362	Anti-POWV Env Domain III Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2c	Neut, ELISA, FC
CABT-YN1245	Anti-POWV Envelope Protein DIII Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1322	Anti-POWV Envelope Protein DIII Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
Poxvirus			
CABT-YN1246	Anti-Poxvirus L1 Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1323	Anti-Poxvirus L1 Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA

Neutralizing Antibodies for Infectious Diseases

Cat_N	Product Name	Antibody Isotype	Applications
Rabies Virus			
CABT-NS1363	Anti-Rabies Virus 67kDa Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	IP, Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1364	Anti-Rabies Virus 67kDa Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	IP, Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1365	Anti-Rabies Virus 67kDa Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Dog, IgG2	IP, Neut, WB, ELISA
CABT-YN1046	Anti-Rabies Virus Surface Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	ELISA, IF, IHC, Neut
CABT-YN1170	Anti-Rabies Virus Monoclonal Antibody, FITC	Mouse, IgG2a	ELISA, IF, IHC, Neut, WB
CABT-YN1250	Anti-Rabies Virus Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, FC
CABT-YN1326	Anti-Rabies Virus Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Neut, FC
Reovirus			
CABT-YN1175	Anti-Reovirus Type 3 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	FC, IF, Neut, RIA
CABT-YN1276	Anti-Reovirus σ 1 Protein T3D Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	IF, Neut, HAI, FC
CABT-YN1352	Anti-Reovirus σ 1 Protein T3D Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	IF, Neut, HAI, FC
Respiratory Syncytial Virus (RSV)			
CABT-NS1025	Anti-BRSV Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA, Crystallization
CABT-NS1026	Anti-BRSV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA, Crystallization
CABT-NS1366	Anti-RSV G Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1367	Anti-RSV G Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1368	Anti-RSV G Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1369	Anti-RSV Fusion Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Ferret, IgG1	Neut, IF
CABT-YN1053	Anti-RSV Fusion Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, FuncS
CABT-YN1054	Anti-RSV Fusion Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG1	ELISA, FuncS
CABT-YN1055	Anti-RSV PAb	Goat, IgG	ELISA, ICC, IF, Neut, Inhib
CABT-YN1058	Anti-RSV Fusion Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	ELISA, Neut
CABT-YN1060	Anti-RSV Fusion Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	ELISA, IF, Neut
CABT-YN1149	Anti-RSV A2 F Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	WB, BL
CABT-YN1255	Anti-RSV G Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
			ELISA

Neutralizing Antibodies for Infectious Diseases

Cat_N	Product Name	Antibody Isotype	Applications
CABT-YN1331	Anti-RSV G Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
Rift Valley Fever Virus (RVFV)			
CABT-YN1257	Anti-RVFV Envelope Proteins Gn Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, FC, SPR
CABT-YN1333	Anti-RVFV Envelope Proteins Gn Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, FC, SPR
Ross River Virus (RRV)			
CABT-YN1195	Anti-RRV E2 Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, Neut
CABT-YN1196	Anti-RRV E2 Protein B Domain Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, Neut
Rotavirus			
CABT-YN1176	Anti-Rotavirus (multi Serotypes) PAb	Mouse,	ELISA, IF, Neut
CABT-YN1177	Anti-Rotavirus DS-1 Serotype II PAb	Mouse	IF, Neut
CABT-YN1197	Anti-Rotavirus VP6 Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, Neut, FC
CABT-YN1253	Anti-Rotavirus VP7 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, Inhib
CABT-YN1329	Anti-Rotavirus VP7 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, Inhib
Rubella Virus (RuV)			
CABT-NS1370	Anti-RuV-1 Coat Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1371	Anti-RuV-1 Coat Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1372	Anti-RuV-1 Coat Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1080	Anti-RuV E1 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	WB, IF, Neut
Sendai Virus			
CABT-NS1382	Anti-Sendai Virus HN Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	HAI, Neut, IF
Simian Immunodeficiency Virus (SIV)			
CABT-YN1266	Anti-SIV Envelope Spikes Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1267	Anti-SIVmac239 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1342	Anti-SIV Envelope Spikes Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1343	Anti-SIVmac239 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA

Neutralizing Antibodies for Infectious Diseases

Cat_N	Product Name	Antibody Isotype	Applications
Sudan Virus (SUDV)			
CABT-YN1274	Anti-SUDV Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA, BL
CABT-YN1350	Anti-SUDV Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA, BL
Suid Herpesvirus (SuHV)			
CABT-NS1383	Anti-SuHV-1 gH Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	IS, Neut
CABT-NS1384	Anti-SuHV-1 gH Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	IS, Neut
Tick-borne Encephalitis Virus (TBEV)			
CABT-NS1385	Anti-TBEV gE Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut, RIA, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1386	Anti-TBEV gE Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Neut, RIA, WB, ELISA
CABT-NS1388	Anti-TBEV Env Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA, IF
CABT-YN1210	Anti-LIV or TBEV EDIII Monoclonal Antibody	Human, scFv	Neut, FuncS
CABT-YN1369	Anti-LIV or TBEV EDIII Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, scFv	Neut, FuncS
CABT-NS1389	Anti-TBEV and LIV Env Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	Neut, ELISA, IF
CABT-NS1390	Anti-TBEV and LIV Env Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut, ELISA, IF
Transmissible Gastroenteritis Virus (TGEV)			
CABT-NS1391	Anti-TGEV S Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut, RIA, WB, ELISA
CABT-YN1183	Anti-TGEV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	IA, Neut, Inhib
CABT-YN1211	Anti-TGEV Monoclonal Antibody	Human, Fab	Neut, ELISA
Vaccinia Virus (VACV)			
CABT-YN1212	Anti-VACV Antigen A33 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, Fab fragment	WB, ELISA, FuncS
CABT-YN1371	Anti-VACV Antigen A33 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, Fab	WB, ELISA, FuncS
CABT-NS1392	Anti-VACV A33 Glycoprotein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2b	Neut, IF
Varicella-Zoster Virus (VZV)			
CABT-YN1048	Anti-VZV gH Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG1	ICC, IF, IP, Neut, Inhib
CABT-YN1279	Anti-VZV gHgL Complex Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1282	Anti-VZV gB Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA

Neutralizing Antibodies for Infectious Diseases

Cat_N	Product Name	Antibody Isotype	Applications
CABT-YN1355	Anti-VZV gHgL Complex Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1358	Anti-VZV gB Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
Venezuelan Equine Encephalitis Virus (VEEV)			
CABT-NS1393	Anti-VEEV Env2 A domain Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-NS1394	Anti-VEEV Env2 B domain Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut
CABT-YN1281	Anti-VEEV TC-83 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1357	Anti-VEEV TC-83 Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
Vesicular Stomatitis Virus (VSV)			
CABT-YN1213	Anti-VSV NP Monoclonal Antibody	Human, VHH	Inhib
CABT-YN1372	Anti-VSV NP Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, VHH	Inhib
West Nile Virus (WNV)			
CABT-NS1395	Anti-WNV Env DI-DII Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Neut
CABT-YN1191	Anti-WNV NS3 Protease Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG3	WB, IP, BL, Neut
CABT-YN1192	Anti-WNV/DENV Env Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	Neut
CABT-YN1199	Anti-WNV NS1 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, FC
CABT-YN1200	Anti-WNV NS1 Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	ELISA, FC
CABT-YN1283	Anti-WNV Surface Proteins E Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1284	Anti-WNV Envelope Protein DIII Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1285	Anti-WNV NS1c Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1359	Anti-WNV Surface Proteins E Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1360	Anti-WNV Envelope Protein DIII Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1361	Anti-WNV NS1c Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA
Yellow Fever Virus (YFV)			
CABT-NS1396	Anti-YFV Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	FuncS, RIA, ELISA, FC, IF
CABT-NS1397	Anti-YFV Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2a	FuncS, RIA, ELISA, FC, IF
CABT-NS1398	Anti-YFV Env Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	FuncS, IP, Neut, ELISA

Neutralizing Antibodies for Infectious Diseases

Cat_N	Product Name	Antibody Isotype	Applications
Zika Virus (ZIKV)			
CABT-NS1399	Anti-ZIKV Env Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA, FC
CABT-NS1400	Anti-ZIKV Env DIII Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgM	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1402	Anti-ZIKV Env Monoclonal Antibody	Rabbit, IgG	Inhib, WB, ELISA, FC
CABT-NS1403	Anti-ZIKV Env Monoclonal Antibody	Ferret, IgG1	Neut, ELISA, FC
CABT-NS1404	Anti-ZIKV EDE Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgM	Neut
CABT-NS1406	Anti-ZIKV Env Domain II Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgM	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1407	Anti-ZIKV Env Domain III Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgM	Neut, ELISA
CABT-NS1408	Anti-ZIKV Env DIII Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2c	Neut, FC
CABT-YN1207	Anti-ZIKV Envelope Protein Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG2c	ELISA, Neut, WB
CABT-YN1287	Anti-ZIKV DIII Lateral Ridge and Dengue Virus DII Monoclonal Antibody	Human, IgG	Neut, ELISA
CABT-YN1363	Anti-ZIKV DIII Lateral Ridge and Dengue Virus DII Monoclonal Antibody	Mouse, IgG	Neut, ELISA

*Application Abbreviation:

- Neut-Neutralization
- ELISA-Enzyme-linked Immunosorbent Assay
- ABA-Affinity Binding Assay
- Inhib-Inhibition
- FC-Flow Cytometry
- IF-Immunofluorescence
- HAI-Hemagglutination
- FuncS-Functional Studies
- BL-Blocking
- IP-Immunoprecipitation
- RIA-Radioimmunoassay
- EM-Electron Microscopy
- WB-Western Blot
- IHC-Immunohistochemistry
- ICC-Immunocytochemistry
- SPR-Surface Plasmon Resonance
- IS-Immunostaining
- IA-Immunoassay
- IHC-P-Immunohistochemistry (Formalin/PFA-fixed paraffin-embedded sections)
- ChIP-Chromatin Immunoprecipitation
- IHC-Fr-Immunohistochemistry (Frozen sections)
- IC-Immunochromatography

CREATIVE DIAGNOSTICS

Neutralizing Antibodies for Infectious Diseases

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